

Mapping Heritage in South Asia: A Multi-Source Geospatial Framework for Spatially Explicit Documentation of Archaeological Sites using Machine Learning and Open-Source Data Platform (Arches)

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Summary

The Mapping Archaeological Heritage in South Asia (MAHSA) project has developed a multi-source geospatial framework to improve documentation of archaeological heritage in South Asia. It integrates legacy datasets, georeferenced Survey of India historical maps, machine-learning feature detection, and ground-truthing field surveys into the Arches platform. This approach addresses long-standing issues of spatial inaccuracy in older records and significantly enhances heritage site identification. Results show thousands of newly detected features and improved precision for legacy sites, visualised through bivariate mapping and the Arches platform. The methodology is transferable, supports SDG 11.4, and strengthens heritage management through reproducible, open-science practices.

KEYWORDS: GIS, SDG, Archaeology, Open-Source Spatial Data, Remote Sensing

1. Introduction

The large-scale documentation and identification of endangered archaeological and cultural heritage is fundamental to achieving the aims set out in Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11.4, which focusses on efforts to protect and safeguard the world's cultural and natural heritage (UNSD, 2025; Huck, 2022; Xiao et al., 2018). In the context of South Asia, the urgency of this task is apparent. Rapid development is resulting in rapid urbanisation and agriculture expansion that threatens recorded and unrecorded heritage sites, often leading to their destruction or irreversible damage before they can be protected or in some cases even formally documented (Conesa et al., 2022; Garcia-Molsosa et al., 2023). While archaeological and cultural heritage sites and monuments in Pakistan and India are protected in principle, in practice they are still often viewed as impediments.

A critical barrier to effective heritage management in South Asia, just like other regions, is inaccuracy or imprecision about the spatial accuracy of documented heritage information, and up-to-date information about states of preservation. Previous research in the region, specifically *the Land, Water and Settlement* (2007–2014) and *TwoRains* (2015–2021) projects, highlighted the extent of these issues through systematic ground-truthing and pilot remote sensing studies in northwest India (Petrie et al., 2017; Green et al., 2019). These projects demonstrated that while extensive 'Legacy Data' (LD) exists

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(e.g. textual records, and site lists derived from earlier surveys, such as Joshi et al. [1984], Possehl [1999], and Mughal [1997]), these records often lack geospatial precision compared to modern standards. This is largely because many of these sites were recorded in a pre-GPS era, so their locations are frequently represented by ambiguous coordinate references, proximity to modern villages, or other contemporary landmarks (e.g. temples, bridges) that may have since changed (Green and Petrie, 2018; Vidyarthi and Chauhan 2025). Consequently, these sites are often spatially misrepresented or effectively ‘lost’ in the landscape (Petrie et al., 2025).

Simultaneously, the Survey of India (SoI) historical map series represents a distinct, under-utilised historical archive usable for large-scale archaeological heritage mapping (Petrie et al. 2019, 2025). Building upon the work of prior projects, this paper introduces the methodological framework and ongoing efforts of the MAHSA project. We address the spatial quality issues by integrating these legacy datasets with historical mapping and modern geospatial technologies within the Arches open-source geospatial relational database platform.

2. Methodology

Figure 1 - Overview of the MAHSA open-source geospatial framework.

The MAHSA project uses a multi-source data integration framework designed for reproducibility and methodological transferability, with an emphasis on open science and data quality (**Figure 1**). Our workflow synthesises four distinct data inputs: (1) Legacy Data; (2) historical topographic maps; (3) Machine Learning (ML) site detection; and (4) on-site field survey via the open-source OpenDataKit (ODK) collection platform. The curated data inputs are then hosted in the Arches geospatial database (<https://www.databasemahsa.org/en/>).

2.1 Data Sources & Integration

The first data input involves the digitisation and standardisation of Legacy Data (LD). We have compiled and cleaned site location data from major twentieth and twenty first century archaeological publications. These datasets often suffer from low spatial accuracy and/or precision, missing values, or ambiguity. Many of the common spatial uncertainty differences often observed in GIS and Remote Sensing (Atkinson and Foody, 2002).

To improve this, we integrate a **second data input**: the georeferenced SoI 1-inch to 1-mile historical map series (editions published largely between 1870–1947). These maps systematically documented topography, including elevated mounds (hachured or form-line features) often archaeological in nature (Petrie et al. 2019; also Green et al., 2019).

The third input utilises Machine Learning and Remote Sensing to scale up site identification and validate legacy locations. We employ deep learning segmentation strategies, specifically Region-based Convolutional Neural Networks (R-CNN) and satellite imagery (Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2) using Google Earth Engine to automatically extract archaeological mound features from the historical maps (Garcia et al. 2021; Berganzo-Besga et al., 2023; also Orengo et al., 2020). While this study focuses on the overall project framework, we refer to the Berganzo-Besga et al. (2023) article for specific details on mound extraction from historical maps utilised in the MAHSA framework.

The fourth data input – based on ground-truthing survey work - comes via our team working in collaboration with researchers based in India and Pakistan. The results are collected in the field and compiled through a customised ODK form used in conjunction with Kobo Toolbox. The use of ODK allows disparate field teams to collect data in a standardised format that is compatible with Arches.

2.2 Arches Platform

These multi-source data inputs are integrated into the Arches heritage data management platform. The Arches platform was initially developed and financed collaboratively by the *Getty Conservation Institute (GCI)* and the *World Monuments Fund (WMF)*. We utilise Arches for its open-source architecture and semantic interoperability, based on the CIDOC-CRM ontology (Myers et al., 2012). This ensures that the resulting dataset is standardised and adheres to FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al 2016), facilitating data sharing between academic researchers and heritage practitioners in Pakistan and India.

3. Application & Results

Figure 2 - Bivariate map comparing the distribution of original Legacy Data points against the new datasets generated

MAHSA’s mapping and identification of archaeological heritage sites has demonstrated a significant improvement in spatial data quality for many of the previously recorded LD locations, resulting in a significant increase in the number of identified potential heritage sites. In **figure 2** we utilise a gridded bivariate map to visualise the spatial discrepancy and density differences between the ‘old’ Legacy Data locations and the corrected, high precision. This visualisation highlights the substantial impact the project has had in revealing clusters of sites that were previously “hidden in plain sight” (Petrie et al., 2025). Many of the areas, coloured in orange and brown, contain archaeological heritage sites that were derived from the historical maps, but were absent from LD sources. The bivariate map identifies areas where legacy data was spatially inaccurate, or where ongoing survey coverage has been insufficient. For example, in the southern regions of Pakistan, an area that has a higher concentration of LD points but is not yet mapped or surveyed.

Furthermore, **table 1** presents a summary table detailing the quantitative results of this integration. Preliminary results indicate that the pilot implementation of the automated detection methods identified nearly 7,500 mound features over a 470,500 km² area, a density significantly higher than that recorded in legacy datasets (Berganzo-Besga et al., 2023). Table 1, together with the bivariate map, illustrates the progress of the data gap; for instance, a high percentage of ML-detected features do not correspond to any previously recorded legacy site, possibly indicating an area of undocumented archaeological heritage that needs further investigation.

Table 1 - The table provides a summary table of counts and percentages of: 1. **Legacy Data (LD)**; 2. **ML- Detected features**; 3. **Verified heritage locations** (validated through MAHSA’s QGIS and PostgreSQL Database (CDB) and ongoing ground-truthing (using ODK) field survey efforts:

Category	Metric	Count	Percentage
Baseline	Legacy Data (LD) locations	7,513	
	SoI Sheets with activity	1,145	
ML Automated Detection	ML-detected features	7,470	
Verified Heritage Locations	Survey polygons	2,133	28.4% of LD
	Survey points	2,119	28.2% of LD
Progress according to sheet coverage	SoI sheets with improvement activity	782	68.3% of sheets
	LD SoI sheets improved	309	27.0% of sheets

4. Broader Implications

This heritage mapping methodology has transferable applications that extend beyond the specific context of South Asian archaeology and heritage. This work directly addresses the GISRUK theme of "People, Planet, and Progress", bridging academic research and heritage management. Additionally, the use of ODK helps with capacity building in collaborating institutes, providing a user-friendly method to record complex heritage information on the field. These methods are applicable to other regions or disciplines tasked with similar endangered heritage and legacy data, as evidenced by work done in Arcadia sister projects such as the *Mapping Africa’s Endangered Archaeological Sites and Monuments* (MAEASaM), *the Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa* (EAMENA) and *Central Asian Archaeological Landscapes* (CAAL) projects.

Use of the Arches platform ensures accessibility for policymaking and community engagement, encouraging a sustainable approach to heritage protection that is resilient to the pressures of development (Myers et al., 2012). The reproducibility of the ML and data integration workflow suggests that these methods are highly transferable to other regions with similar cartographic legacies, such as in Europe, the Middle East or parts of Africa, where historical maps remain an under-utilised resource for SDG 11.4 monitoring (Conesa et al., 2022; Roberts et al., 2021). The integration of historic maps as a “multifaceted resource” assist in site discovery and provides a baseline against which modern environmental changes can be measured (Roberts et al., 2021).

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study illustrates how the combination of novel geospatial methods, historical archival data, Machine Learning and on-site documentation can support endangered archaeological heritage management. By enriching Legacy Data, matching it with spatially explicit features extracted from historical maps using machine learning and on-site survey validation, we provide a robust foundation for future research opportunities, both on a regional and large-scale level. By quantifying our current work using the bivariate map and summary tables, we aim to illustrate the potential of such integrated techniques and to promote wider use of the created resource. By doing so, this work makes a tangible contribution towards achieving SDG 11.4, ensuring that the rich archaeological heritage of South Asia is not lost to the rapid progress of the present-day urban and agriculture developments.

6. Acknowledgements

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8. Biographies

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